

From impact factor to responsible evaluation

Overview of developments in research assessment and implications for EUTOPIA

Lennart Stoy (VUB) and Elisa Maes (VUB)

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Introduction

EUTOPIA-TRAIN is implementing a transformation module which aims to introduce an [“academic career systems that support and reward researchers who participate in engaging with society and in a culture of sharing the results of their research, in particular by ensuring early sharing and open access to their publications and other research outputs”](#). Specifically, Task 3.3 of EUTOPIA-TRAIN seeks to *“Design framework policies for research assessment which reflect Open Science practices and adopt a timetable for implementation”*.

This is part of a wider strategic agenda of the European Commission. Research assessment reform – in conjunction with advancing Open Science – has grown into a major reform program aiming to create a system in which researchers and research activities are [“evaluated on their intrinsic merits and performance rather than on the number of publications and where they are published, promoting qualitative judgement with peer-review, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.”](#) This objective is also anchored in the [Conclusions on the future governance of the European Research Area](#) and the [Pact for Research & Innovation in Europe](#).

This briefing serves as a background document for participants in the respective EUTOPIA activities. It explains the rationale behind research assessment reform, sketches the political momentum and stakeholder activities around research assessment reform, present the dimensions of assessment used in recent frameworks, discusses implications for EUTOPIA, and outlines the main activities foreseen by EUTOPIA-TRAIN in the pursuit of this activity.

The case for research assessment reform

Universities today heavily rely on bibliometric indicators and research income to assess research and researchers. In a survey conducted by the European University Association (EUA) in 2019, 90 percent of more than 190 responding institutions indicated that journal publications were very important or important for assessment – widely outpacing most other indicators for assessment (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Most relevant indicators for assessing academic work

Source: Saenen, Bregt. (2019, September 17). 2019 Open Science survey results on research assessment. Open Science FAIR 2019 (OSFAIR 2019), Porto, Portugal. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3435325>

However, over the recent years, quantitative and bibliometric approaches to measure and incentivise research ‘excellence’ and ‘impact’ have been subject to rising, vocal criticism. [Aubert Bonn and Bouter \(2021\)](#) identify five types of overarching problems. Table 1 presents these five types and provides examples. Taken together, they highlight why bibliometrics should be used cautiously.

Table 1 Critique of common assessment approaches¹

Problem according to Aubert Bonn and Bouter (2021)	Description and examples
<p>“An exaggerated focus on research outputs”</p>	<p><i>Basing assessment on narrow types of outputs does not represent a holistic assessment of the academic track record of individuals. Open Science activities (e.g., data sharing, code and software sharing, registered reports or data publications) are not represented, as are steps in the research process such as research data management or contributing to peer review.</i></p> <p>Publishing research results is only one activity among many others which researchers do. However, teaching and providing services and other essential tasks such as mentoring, reviewing or team contributions almost always take second place or are even ignored in research assessments. Activities and processes that provide information on how research is conducted are largely ignored from output-oriented assessments, creating a culture "that cares exclusively about what is achieved and not about how it is achieved". Detailed methods, the approaches, the specific contributions, or the translation of research in practice are rarely considered in research assessments. This risks losing sight of important procedural aspects thought to be highly important in advancing science, such as quality, integrity, and transparency.</p>
<p>“Quantity over quality”</p>	<p><i>Overreliance on performance indicators can incentivize problematic research practices or even misconduct by driving the competition to only publish specific results, to publish in specific journals or to increase citation counts.</i></p> <p>Quantitative performance indicators can have the effect that “norms and criteria for scientific quality, e.g. epistemic originality, long-term scientific progress, societal relevance, and social responsibility, receive less attention”. Research found that retractions, data falsification and errors are more often found in high-impact journals. In addition, predatory publishers benefit from authors desperate to publish regardless of quality (Hedding 2019; Vogel 2017).</p>
<p>“Inappropriate use of metrics”</p>	<p><i>Current bibliometric indicators should not be used for individual evaluations given a lack of robustness of the indicators and their underlying data, as well about the concepts they intend to capture:</i></p> <p>Journal impact factors (JIF) are a <i>journal-level</i> metric and were not meant as a measure for the quality or impact of individual papers or research. The inventor of the Journal Impact Factor himself “warned against using journal impact factors for assessing individual scholarly articles”. Research suggests that “the citation performance of individual papers cannot be inferred from the JIF”. Moreover, Journal impact factors can be artificially inflated.</p> <p>Seeing a lack of transparent data underlying impact factors, some argue that “Just as scientists would not accept the findings in a scientific paper without seeing the primary data, so should they not rely on Thomson Scientific's impact factor, which is based on hidden data”. Moreover, impact factors can be negotiated, and to some therefore resemble “subjective judgments of journal quality” than appropriate indicators of research quality.</p> <p>In parallel to the JIF, the inventor of the h-index himself stated that the h-index can “fail spectacularly and have severe unintended negative consequences”. Bibliometrics experts have argued that it “cannot be considered an appropriate indicator of a scientist’s overall scientific impact”, emphasising that “in the case of young scientists publication and citation statistics are only of limited value”.</p> <p>Citations can be manipulated as a result of “competition for research funding and high-quality journal space coupled with the intense focus on a single measure of performance, the number of publications or grants”. Research found that citations, with differences across author</p>

¹ The table and its contents, including many sources, are based on [Aubert Bonn and Bouter \(2021\)](#) and [Plomb, Schettino and Tsang \(2021\)](#).

Problem according to Aubert Bonn and Bouter (2021)	Description and examples
	<p>networks, can correlate with “positive study outcomes, the authority of its authors, and the journal in which that article is published.”</p>
<p>“Narrow views of impact”</p>	<p><i>The impact of education, management roles and leadership, knowledge transfer, innovation, entrepreneurship or community service activities are not easily quantifiable – and the perceived relevance of different types of impact varies widely by discipline.</i></p> <p>Other types of academic activity such as teaching and ‘service’ have lost relevance over time compared to research outputs. While the public dimensions of research – outside academia – are often mentioned in assessment framework, often “there are neither explicit incentives, nor clear structures of support for assessing the contributions of scholarship to the various dimensions of publicness”.</p> <p>Bibliometric indicators, on the other hand, only consider recognition and visibility within the scientific (and citing) community and provide a restricted view of impact. Requiring publications in specific English-language journals exacerbates this and “systematically pushes scientists to publish in cost-prohibitive, foreign language journals and creates unnecessary barriers between science and its potential beneficiaries”. This may also act as a barrier to interdisciplinary work</p> <p>Where there is a strong focus on bibliometrics there is also a risk of putting “less value on learning how to realize the potential benefit of [...] application”, and therefore missing to capture the practical or societal impact of research..</p>
<p>“Obstacle to diversity”</p>	<p><i>Assessment based on citation metrics and publication outputs can have adverse effects on diversity, for instance in relation to gender, disability, world regions, or languages, posing challenges from the perspective of diversity and inclusion.</i></p> <p>Women are underrepresented as first authors, publish more with domestic rather than international co-authors and “articles with women in dominant author positions receive fewer citations than those with men in the same positions”. Based on contributorship data, women are more likely to perform research and experimental tasks compared to other contributions (such as study design, data analysis or writing) mentioned in journal articles Moreover, “women faculty perform more service than male faculty in academia”. Women were also more affected by Covid-19, publishing less and launching fewer projects.</p> <p>Problems have been identified regarding researchers reporting disabilities or minority researchers, who both seem to face reduced funding success rates. Further, abstract ratings have been demonstrated to be lower when assigned to origins in lower-income countries compared with high-income countries. Moreover, lower ranked journals, for example in the field of higher education studies, have been found to be “statistically more likely to include research and researchers from outside of the core anglophone countries, making an important contribution to the diversity of scholarship beyond the dominating western and English-language discourse.”</p>

The critique has translated into academic activism: Young researchers call for change of metric-driven assessments to increase diversity, equity, and inclusion, but also [“to promote high-quality research”](#), adopting the stance that bibliometric indicators fail at capturing research quality in a meaningful way. The Marie Curie Alumni Association warns that [“narrow notions of research excellence suppress researchers’ development, creativity, and engagement, to the detriment of advances in knowledge and society”](#).

Other scholars argue that [“Relying on a limited set of proxy measures, current systems of evaluation fail to recognize and reward the many dependencies upon which a healthy scholarly ecosystem relies”](#), stressing that publishing requires invisible work, such as peer review. According to some

advocates, a solution could come in form of a [“more balanced system of rewards, one that supports collaborative practices \(for example in terms of data sharing\), transparency \(for example in terms of peer review\) and effective value and impact \(through article content analysis and article-level rather than journal-level metrics\)”](#).

Translating these concerns into tangible change is the goal of bottom-up initiatives such as the *San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment* ([DORA](#)) or [The Leiden Manifesto](#) for research metrics, both of which provide principles for reforming research assessment – such as responsible use of metrics - and to reduce the focus on quantitative bibliometric indicators overall. The [Hong Kong Principles](#) aim to foster “trustworthiness, rigor, and transparency” and stress the need to better recognise and reward research integrity. Finally, [The Metric Tide](#) has been a pivotal report in raising awareness about the pitfalls of over relying on indicators with inherent flaws and introducing the concept of “responsible metrics”.

Brewing political momentum

The notion that current assessment systems are ripe for change has not remained isolated within the academic community. Political momentum, especially through the Open Science agenda, has led to many high-level **initiatives around reforming research assessment in Europe**:

- The 2020 [Communication on the Future of the European Research Area](#) bemoans that “the current research assessment system is largely based on the impact factors associated with specific journals, where the publication takes place, rather than on the individual content and added-value of the publication itself”.
- The May 2021 [Council conclusions on the European Universities initiative](#) sees alliances “as ‘testbeds’ for innovative teaching and for research, including academic career assessment and rewarding systems that take into account inter alia open science practices, quality of teaching, transfer of knowledge and outreach”. The ‘European University’ is therefore an instrument to realise the EU’s strategic goals on research assessment.
- In parallel, the next [revision of the European Charter for Researchers and a Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers](#) may include Open Science and new forms of research assessment, indicating that “the assessment dimension of the C&C should be reinforced so that Open Science, quality over quantity of research outputs, and Gender Equality in research are duly fostered.”
- The [Pact for Research & Innovation in Europe](#) calls member states and the Commission to “further develop current research assessment systems for research, researchers, teams and institutions, to reward quality, impact, open science practices, leadership and engagement with society and collaboration with industry; consider a wide range of research outputs and activities and allow for diverse career paths”.
- **Horizon Europe**, Europe’s major funding programme, also introduced Open Science as part of the excellence criteria and includes measures to move away from publication-driven evaluation. The **ERC** has already [banned JIFs from being used in evaluations](#).

At global level, research assessment reform has been included in the [UNESCO recommendation on Open Science](#). It recommends that UNESCO members should “review research assessment and career evaluation systems in order to align them with the principles of Open Science”.

Other public and private non-profit research funders are embedding Open Science in research assessment and work on reducing metrics-driven assessment in their programmes. Notably, funders active in **Plan S** [expect alignment with DORA or similar declarations](#) from beneficiary institutions. The **Wellcome Trust** has released detailed guidance on “[responsible and fair approaches for research assessment](#)” to this end.

Where change is happening

Advocacy groups. Changing research assessment is not only a priority of political actors. Major European research and education stakeholders have also declared research assessment reform a focus of their work for the next years.

- The **European University Association** (EUA) has warned against misuse of certain metrics, stating that “[‘proxy’ assessment tools like the journal impact factor should now be banned as a direct measure for research quality.](#)” EUA has [analysed the state of research assessment practices](#) in Europe and shared [good practices](#) that can inspire action at other universities.
- **Science Europe** has a similar priority and developed [comprehensive recommendations on improving research assessment systems](#). These include the recommendation to increase the use of qualitative assessment methods compared to more traditional quantitative indicators.
- **LERU** have also been vocal about [revising assessment systems in the context of Open Science](#) and has developed a [practical roadmap for universities](#).
- **CESAER** has compiled a [set of potential indicators for Open Science and other academic activities](#) that can support the transition to a different assessment system.

National initiatives. At national level, several university associations or national platforms have released guidelines how to change research assessment.

- A **Finnish initiative** convened by the Confederation of Finnish Learned Societies developed a [comprehensive guideline for academic assessment](#). The recommendation includes a clear commitment to responsible use of metrics and that quantitative indicators should only be used to complement qualitative approaches. The recommendations have been endorsed by the Finnish Rectors’ Conference.
- The **Norwegian Rectors’ Conference** likewise developed a framework for recognition and rewards in academic career ([NOR-CAM](#)). The framework emphasizes the need for “Assessing and recognising a greater breadth of competencies” as well as the “need to reduce and modify the reliance on quantitative publication metrics”.
- The **Dutch 2021-2027 Standard Evaluation Protocol** ([SEP](#)), developed by a group of Dutch research organisations, stresses that “many academics feel there is a one-sided emphasis on research performance, frequently leading to the undervaluation of the other key areas such as education, impact, leadership and (for university medical centres) patient care.” Consequently, the SEP seeks to “enable greater diversity in possible career paths and profiles”, which goes hand in hand with “a reduced emphasis on quantitative results (such as number of publications) and a greater emphasis on quality, content, scientific integrity, creativity, contribution to science, academia and/or society, and acknowledgement of the academic’s specific profile and domain”. Universities and research organizations in the Netherlands will implement this vision from 2021 onward.

- The European Commission has itself released a framework supporting the development of research assessment with a strong view on Open Science practices. This **Open Science Career Assessment Matrix** ([OS-CAM](#)) has been a reference document for many of the initiatives mentioned above.

Many of the initiatives presented above do not limit their focus to the assessment of research activities. Rather, many seek to balance research, education, and other academic activities in more holistic approaches in a wider move to improve research culture. EUA emphasizes that the term “academic assessment” should therefore be preferred over “research assessment”, observing that [“discussions on responsible practices were initially limited to ‘research’ assessment, the scope of the debate has since been broadened to include the incentives and rewards available for all academic activities, i.e., education, research, and innovation in service to society.”](#)

Individual universities as frontrunners. A likely reason why reform has been moving slowly is that institutions perceive a [“first mover disadvantage”](#). They do not want to risk falling behind in rankings, receiving less performance-based funding, or harming the careers of researchers whose success might rely on other universities still using traditional indicators. Nonetheless, several universities in Europe have emerged as ‘frontrunners’ of research assessment reform:

- **Ghent University** is a frequently mentioned example, where the basis for change was the realization that [“an excessive focus on quantitative indicators compromises the quality of the research”](#). The [vision statement](#) formulates eight building blocks based on a better balance between indicator-driven and peer-review driven assessments, as well as a proper application of such methods in a flexible manner.
- **Utrecht University**, based on the Dutch SEP and the national programme surrounding it, has released a [institutional model for assessment procedures](#) around six elements related to education, research and professional performance. The model seeks to support excellence in specific areas and to stimulate diversity of profiles and careers. Finally, it aims to allow “setting qualitative and narrative driven goals, rather than using quantitative indicators”.
- The **Open University of Catalonia** is implementing a [Open Knowledge Action Plan](#), which includes an action on evaluation of researchers. The university has set up a DORA Working Group and a respective action plan to develop recommendations. Practical changes include changing criteria for internal calls, indicators used for research evaluation, and the criteria used for recruitment and promotion of research personnel.
- **University College London** introduced a [Bibliometrics Policy](#) in early 2020. The policy defines principles for the responsible use of metrics following the commitment to “valuing research and researchers based on their own merits, not the merits of metrics”. Moreover, UCL’s [Academic Career Framework](#) specifies that, as a DORA signatory, “Research activity is described with reference to qualitative and quantitative evidence of achievement, including appreciation by peers, impact, scale, originality, rigour and significance of research outputs”.
- **Cambridge University** has signed DORA and [developed guidelines on the responsible use of metrics in assessment](#), which state “they should only be used to inform and support but not supplant qualitative expert assessment. The limitations of any metric must be recognised and acknowledged”, and adding requirements on transparency, appropriateness for specific disciplines and career stages.

- **Warwick University**, a EUTOPIA member, has developed a set of [principles for evaluation of research](#) based on the Leiden Manifesto. These principles are currently being translated into practice by reviewing processes, documents (such as templates), and indicators used at central and department level.

Dimensions of assessment

Assessment reform is intimately linked to the question which activities, outputs or impacts are valued as important parts of academic work. Much of the criticism of current assessment methods stems from the observation that there is a de-facto overreliance on research articles and bibliometric indicators, either through explicit criteria or, also, norms and expectations of reviewers.

Addressing these structural challenges therefore relies on three interconnected actions:

1. Broadening the types of outputs and activities that are considered in assessments, in particular Open Science
2. Decreasing usage of quantitative indicators and emphasizing qualitative, contextual assessment
3. Balancing the importance of research, education and other academic activities

The breadth of activities that can be considered under point 3) is visible in the major dimensions of several evaluation and assessment frameworks mentioned above and, for reference, the evaluation matrix for tenured researchers as VUB (Table 2). While there are differences in nuances, they all tend to cover research, education, notions of scientific or societal impact and dissemination, as well as leadership and professional conduct.

Notably, the high-level dimensions of VUB’s assessment matrix do not differ widely from the other examples although it has not yet undergone a review with a specific focus on responsible evaluation or Open Science. This highlights **room for incremental changes to existing institutional frameworks**, instead of redeveloping them from scratch. One approach could be to change or broaden suggested indicators or methods for high-level concepts, balancing their relevance, and training reviewers, while the overarching framework remains with minimal changes. This is an approach also suggested by the Dutch research council NWO under the motto ‘[Don’t abolish anything, just broaden the scope](#)’.

Table 2 High-level dimensions of selected assessment frameworks²

Framework	High-level dimensions
NOR-CAM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research output ▪ Research process ▪ Pedagogical competence ▪ Impact and innovation ▪ Leadership ▪ Other experience
OS-CAM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research output ▪ Research process ▪ Service and leadership ▪ Research impact ▪ Teaching and supervision ▪ Professional experience

² The recommended indicators and criteria used by the frameworks, their overarching principles for assessment, e.g. transparency and reflectivity, are not shown here. An exhaustive overview would be too long for this briefing, but can inform later discussions among EUTOPIA members how to measure or evaluate these dimensions. Such action would be crucial for implementing goals 1) and 2) mentioned above.

Framework	High-level dimensions	
Finland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research funding and research supervision and leadership experience ▪ Teaching merits and experience ▪ Awards and honours 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Assessment of scientific and academic merit ▪ Scientific and academic networking and community development
SEP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research products for peers ▪ Use of research products by peers ▪ Marks of recognition by peers ▪ Research products for societal target groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Use of research products by societal target groups ▪ Marks of recognition by societal target groups
Utrecht University	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research ▪ Education ▪ Impact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Professional performance ▪ Team ▪ Leadership
VUB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research ▪ Education 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Service & dissemination ▪ Administrative matters & personnel policy

Implications for EUTOPIA and European Universities

Each EUTOPIA university already operates a system for research assessment. A framework policy for EUTOPIA developed by EUTOPIA-TRAIN should therefore be based on principles such as:

- Subsidiarity: do not replace the existing institutional assessment systems but provide a high-level definition of dimensions and principles that should be present in the institutional assessment systems.
- Alliance values and activities: the EUTOPIA documents do mention specific types of academic activity and impact, including Open Science. To nurture these activities or impacts, a framework policy should acknowledge them.

The EUTOPIA alliance, likely like many other European Universities, seeks to foster different types of impact and academic activities, including Open Science. Examples are the goal to “to promote innovation and societal impact” or to “open up their [the universities’] research structures for society, students and policymakers” ([EUTOPIA-TRAIN](#)). The vision includes making them “attentive to the plurality, potentiality and pre-eminence of Europe’s regions” and to create “powerful place-making partnerships” ([EUTOPIA2050](#)). Elements of the [Values Statement](#) such as the focus on local environments, a culture of inclusion and diversity reflect this thinking.

As emphasised in the section on research assessment reform, aspects of academic work which reflect these ideas, such as societal engagement and collaboration with local stakeholders, multi-disciplinarity, multilingualism, cultural engagement, Open Science cannot always be assumed to be fully recognised in academic assessment exercises.

While EUTOPIA-TRAIN specifically addresses research and Open Science, this implies that **reflecting about research assessment should not take place isolated from other activities in EUTOPIA**, for instance with regard to the alliance’s HR strategy, innovation and entrepreneurship, the research strategy etc. This would be a means for EUTOPIA to move towards framework conditions in which

academics are recognised and rewarded for various types of academic activities and Open Science (either directly in a EUTOPIA-related project or in their usual area of work).³

What EUTOPIA-TRAIN will produce

Task 3.3 of EUTOPIA-TRAIN will develop the **EUTOPIA Framework Policy on Research Assessment**. The term ‘framework policy’ should be understood as a sufficiently flexible document outlining the principles, practices (e.g. related to Open Science), outputs and activities that the EUTOPIA community values, the level of assessment (e.g., individual, research group, project, institution), as well as potential approaches and indicators used in assessment. Figure 2 illustrates the types of deliverables under development.

The framework policy will be translated into more practical ‘**implementation roadmaps**’, which explain how a partner aims to apply the framework policy within their local context. The framework policy will function as a guidance document and toolbox for these roadmaps. The **purpose is therefore not to replace local assessment policies, but to facilitate alignment over a range of dimensions and elements**.

Figure 2 Outputs of EUTOPIA-TRAIN Task 3.3

Besides the institutional framework policy, the task also aims to produce **recommendations how to incentivise and reward Open Science practices through EUTOPIA activities and projects** themselves, for instance by including Open Science elements in proposal forms or evaluations of EUTOPIA fellowships and projects (e.g., EUTOPIA-SIF, YLA).

The development of this framework policy and further documents will take place with broad consultation of internal stakeholders and opportunities for bottom-up conversation. This follows the LERU recommendation that [“Redefining criteria for academic assessment is not a simple top-down process. Involvement and support of the Faculty and the research community is essential”](#).

³ A similar recommendation was recently issued by EUA in the context of universities’ innovation capacities, stating that universities should [“expand career development and recognise a wide range of academic staff contributions in career assessment, including innovation activities. Such activities should be considered in a broader sense, including its economic, social, cultural, ethical and environmental impacts.”](#)

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